

Are schools suitable for information literacy education? Critical reflections and perspectives from Danish lower secondary school

Jan Ole Størup^a

^a Aarhus University, Nordre Ringgade 1, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

1. Abstract

Seldom questioned, schools are depicted as central institutions for fostering critical information literacies among youth – most notably, the abilities to critically search, evaluate, and use information (Haider & Sundin, 2022; Limberg et al., 2008; Sundin, 2025b). One could ask whether and how schools – and teachers – are suited to take on the demanding task of equipping students with the competence necessary – a task complicated further by the advent of generative AI (Berger, 2019; Earp, 2009; Shannon et al., 2019; Shin & Lwin, 2017; Sundin, 2025a; Sural & Dedebeali, 2018; Swart, 2021). In Danish schools, students' perceived opportunities for democratic engagement and participation (Bruun & Lieberkind, 2024; Lieberkind, 2020) and digital information literacy competences are declining (Bundsgaard et al., 2024; Fraillon, 2024). In the hope of addressing such challenges, educational reform and other initiatives such as a 'technology comprehension' subject are implemented in the Danish curriculum. Hence, societies constantly seek to repair the school and its functions to meet changing societal demands (Ball & Collet-Sabé, 2022). This educationalization (Rüsselbæk Hansen, 2024), however, can be argued to distort the very purpose and concern of school, thereby instrumentalizing it as a service made to 'please its customers', i.e., society (Biesta, 2022).

The school institution has historically been bound to the production and regulation of knowledge and docile bodies (Ball & Collet-Sabé, 2025; Foucault, 1995), creating certain possibilities and constraints for being, participating, and learning. The school, some (critical) scholars argue, works as a 'less flawed alternative' or "one node in a network of 'intolerable' institutions" (Ball & Collet-Sabé, 2022:988) that has been marketized within a neoliberal performative logic, calling for resistance (Biesta, 2022) rather than continuous repair and reform.

In response to this, and as an intended provocative (and perhaps naïve) stance, this presentation seeks to take a step back and ask: Why school? Ideally, the school functions as a democratizing and emancipatory institution fostering educated, skillful, and critical citizens able to navigate and relate themselves to the world around them (Biesta, 2022; Collet-Sabé & Ball, 2023). In practice, however, it will be argued here that schools often create notions of the opposite.

This poster examines the school's role in providing students with the competence needed to critically engage with (digital) information. This is done by drawing on empirical material from a PhD project conducted during Danish lower secondary school students' project work. The tentative findings suggest that students' information literacy practices (i.e. searching and evaluating information) risk becoming shaped by and entangled within classroom processes of individualization, instrumentalization, and alienation due to the simultaneously ubiquitous and opaque demands towards students' performances and outputs. Such structural barriers may hinder students' critical engagements with underlying mechanisms of search engines and other elements of contemporary information landscapes.

Is it time to rethink the idea of schooling as part of information literacy education? Importantly, this presentation is not conclusive in answering these questions but rather seeks to initiate reflections and

SEASON 2025, September 24–25, 2025, Hamburg, Germany

EMAIL: jos@psy.au.dk (A. 1)

ORCID: 0000-0003-4463-2467 (A. 1)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17156349>

© 2025 Copyright for this paper by its authors.

Use permitted under Creative Commons License Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

inspire critical discussions about the role of the neo-liberal school regarding young people's information literacies anno 2025.

2. Acknowledgements

This poster presentation is supported by a PhD scholarship granted by Aarhus BSS Graduate School. I would like to thank my friend and colleague Nicklas Runge from the Department of Psychology and Behavioural Sciences at Aarhus University for providing helpful feedback on early drafts of the poster abstract. Moreover, I would like to thank the reviewers for valuable comments and pointing out areas of improvement.

3. References

- Ball, S., & Collet-Sabé, J. (2022). Against school: An epistemological critique. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 43(6), 985–999.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2021.1947780>
- Ball, S. J., & Collet-Sabé, J. (2025). *Against School: Thinking Education Differently*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-80415-1>
- Berger, P. (2019). Who needs teachers? Factors associated with learning ICT skills from teachers in a multilevel analysis of the ICILS data. *MedienPädagogik: Zeitschrift Für Theorie Und Praxis Der Medienbildung*, 35, 116–135. <https://doi.org/10.21240/mpaed/35/2019.10.22.X>
- Biesta, G. (2022). School-as-Institution or School-as-Instrument? How to Overcome Instrumentalism without Giving Up on Democracy. *Educational Theory*, 72(3), 319–331.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/edth.12533>
- Bruun, J., & Lieberkind, J. (2024). Politisk og demokratisk dannelse i en krisetid: ICCS 2022 (1ST ED). AARHUS UNIVERSITY PRESS.
- Bundsgaard, J., Bindslev, S., Caeli, E. N., Rasmussen, E., & Grønhøj, E. (2024). Danske elevers teknologiforståelse og skærmbrug: Resultater fra ICILS-undersøgelsen 2023. Aarhus Universitetsforlag.
- Collet-Sabé, J., & Ball, S. J. (2023). Beyond School. The challenge of co-producing and commoning a different episteme for education. *Journal of Education Policy*, 38(6), 895–910.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2022.2157890>
- Earp, V. (2009). Integrating Information Literacy into Teacher Education: A Successful Grant Project. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian*, 28(4), 166–178.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639260903275748>
- Foucault, M. (1995). *Discipline and punish: The birth of the prison* (A. Sheridan, Trans.; Second Vintage Books edition). Vintage Books, a division of Random House, Inc.
- Fraillon, J. (2024). AN INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE ON DIGITAL LITERACY : Results from ICILS 2023. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).
- Haider, J., & Sundin, O. (2022). *Paradoxes of Media and Information Literacy: The Crisis of Information* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003163237>
- Lieberkind, J. (2020). Democracy and togetherness: Between students' educational and political status—a study of primary and lower secondary education in Denmark. *Multicultural Education Review*, 12(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2005615x.2020.1720134>
- Limberg, L., Alexandersson, M., Lantz-Andersson, A., & Folkesson, L. (2008). What Matters? Shaping Meaningful Learning through Teaching Information Literacy. *Libri*, 58(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1515/libr.2008.010>
- Rüsselbæk Hansen, D. (2024). Democratic engagements with negativities in education and public school. *Speki. Nordic Philosophy and Education Review*, 1(1), 43–57.
<https://doi.org/10.5617/speki.11540>

- Shannon, C., Reilly, J., & Bates, J. (2019). Teachers and information literacy: Understandings and perceptions of the concept. *Journal of Information Literacy*, 13(2).
<https://doi.org/10.11645/13.2.2642>
- Shin, W., & Lwin, M. O. (2017). How does “talking about the Internet with others” affect teenagers’ experience of online risks? The role of active mediation by parents, peers, and school teachers. *New Media & Society*, 19(7), 1109–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444815626612>
- Sundin, O. (2025a). Navigating media and information literacy in the age of AI: A view from Sweden. *Revue Internationale d’éducation de Sèvres*, HS-4. <https://doi.org/10.4000/146wg>
- Sundin, O. (2025b). Theorising notions of searching, (re)sources and evaluation in the light of generative AI. *Information Research an International Electronic Journal*, 30(CoLIS), 291–302. <https://doi.org/10.47989/ir30CoLIS52258>
- Sural, S., & Dedeali, N. C. (2018). A Study of Curriculum Literacy and Information Literacy Levels of Teacher Candidates in Department of Social Sciences Education. *European Journal of Educational Research*, volume–7–2018(volume7-issue2.html), 303–317. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.7.2.303>
- Swart, J. (2021). Tactics of news literacy: How young people access, evaluate, and engage with news on social media. *New Media & Society*, 00(0), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211011447>